

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-1-10-IG-5%	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	5	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 1 10
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	45.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	9/23/2021 11:31:00 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:41:47 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.412	1100931	39.19	75250
2	10.360	1106604	39.39	60628
3	11.282	302327	10.76	15113
4	19.763	299618	10.66	8063

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-1-121-IG-5%	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	37	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 1 121
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	2/22/2022 3:08:25 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 3:36:32 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.920	9493485	99.92	610033
2	9.953	140	0.00	64
3	11.254	6885	0.07	664
4	19.232	815	0.01	-54